
Teacher Competence, Motivation, Attitude and Performance of Junior Secondary Schools' Students in Social Studies in Northwest Jigawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of teacher competence, motivation, and attitude on the academic performance of junior secondary school students in Social Studies in Northwest Jigawa State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design and multistage sampling technique were employed. Thirty junior secondary schools were randomly selected from Ringim, Babura, and Gumel education zones. A total of 90 Social Studies teachers and 300 students participated. Data were collected using the Teacher Competency Rating Scale (TCRS), Students' Assessment Test (SAT), and Teacher Motivation and Attitude Questionnaire (TMAQ). The study analyzed data using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and an independent t-test. Findings revealed a positive correlation between teacher competence (subject knowledge, teaching methodology, classroom management, instructional material use, and evaluation strategies), motivation, attitude, and student performance. A significant performance difference was observed between students taught by trained and untrained teachers, while no significant difference was found based on the teacher's gender. The study recommends capacity-building initiatives, professional training, workshops, and improved working conditions for Social Studies teachers.

Keywords: Teacher competence, motivation, attitude, Social Studies, student performance, secondary education

Introduction

Teachers are fundamental to educational success, as their competence, motivation, and attitude significantly influence student learning outcomes. Effective teaching requires mastery of subject content, pedagogical skills, classroom management, instructional resource utilization, and assessment strategies. Scholars have linked student achievement to teacher qualifications (Ubah, 2001; Darling-Hammond, 2000) and school facilities (Owoeye & Yara, 2011), but teacher quality remains the most critical factor (Mua'azu & Maibeni, 2016; Agana, 2010; Siddique, 2010). Alarming, teacher quality has declined, with some educators lacking essential teaching skills (Olakunri, 2001; Olaofe, 2005).

Social Studies, which explores human interactions and problem-solving, relies on effective teachers who are competent, motivated, and well-trained. Assessing teacher effectiveness is crucial for improving instructional quality and enhancing student performance. This study investigates the relationship between teacher competence, motivation, and attitude and the academic performance of junior secondary school students in Social Studies.

Research Objectives

1. Examine the relationship between teacher competence and students' academic performance in Social Studies in secondary schools in Northwest Jigawa State.
2. Determine the relationship between teacher motivation and students' academic performance in Social Studies in secondary schools in Northwest Jigawa State.
3. Assess the relationship between teacher attitude and students' academic performance in Social Studies in secondary schools in Northwest Jigawa State.

Literature Review

Concept of Social Studies

Social Studies is an integrated discipline focusing on the study of human interactions within their environments, aiming to equip learners with problem-solving skills and civic competence. Ololobou (2010) describes it as an organized, integrated study emphasizing cognition, functional skills, and desirable attitudes to produce effective citizens.

Objectives of Social Studies

The integration of social sciences and humanities into Nigeria's Social Studies curriculum aims to:

- i. Develop self-confidence and initiative in students.
- ii. Foster attitudes of cooperation, tolerance, and integrity.
- iii. Promote national consciousness and willingness to embrace change.
- iv. Enhance creativity, resourcefulness, and social awareness.

Teacher Competence

Teacher competence encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary for effective teaching. Roelofs and Sanders (2007) define it as the ability to achieve specific performance levels. In Social Studies, competent teachers possess a deep understanding of subject matter, effective pedagogical strategies, and classroom management skills. A study by Ehi et al. (2020) found a significant positive relationship between teacher qualifications and students' academic performance in Social Studies in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Teacher Motivation

Motivation refers to the underlying reasons for behavior. Lai (2011) describes it as the attribute that moves individuals to act. Intrinsic motivation, driven by personal interest or enjoyment, is crucial for teachers, as it influences their commitment and effectiveness. Muhammad et al. (2020) highlighted that teachers' working conditions and attitudes significantly impact students' academic achievement in Social Studies in North-East Nigeria.

Teacher Attitude

Attitude encompasses an individual's predispositions toward specific entities, influencing behavior. Sharma (2016) defines it as a complex organization of evaluative beliefs, feelings, and action tendencies. Positive teacher attitudes toward teaching and students are linked to improved student outcomes. Research indicates that teachers' attitudes significantly affect students' academic performance in Social Studies.

In summary, teacher competence, motivation, and attitude are critical factors influencing students' academic performance in Social Studies. Enhancing these aspects through targeted professional development and improved working conditions can lead to better educational outcomes.

Methodology

This study adopted a quasi-experimental research design to examine the relationship between teacher competence, motivation, attitude, and students' academic performance in Social Studies. This method was chosen as it allows for investigating relationships in a natural classroom setting while maintaining a degree of control over variables (Johnson, 2011). It is particularly useful when true experimental conditions are impractical due to ethical or logistical constraints (Lenip, 2013).

Population and Sampling

The study targeted junior secondary school Social Studies teachers and students in Northwest Jigawa State. A multistage sampling technique was used:

- Three education zones (Ringim, Babura, and Gumel) were purposively selected.
- From each zone, ten schools were randomly selected, making a total of 30 schools.
- A total of 90 Social Studies teachers (three per school) were selected using stratified and simple random sampling.
- 300 students (ten per school) were randomly sampled.

Instrumentation

Three instruments were used for data collection:

1. Teacher Competence Rating Scale (TCRS), to assess teacher competence in terms of subject matter knowledge, teaching methodology, instructional material usage, classroom management, and evaluation strategies.
2. Teacher Motivation and Attitude Questionnaire (TMAQ), a structured five-point Likert scale measuring teachers' motivation and attitude toward teaching.
3. Students' Assessment Test (SAT) – A standardized test evaluating students' knowledge in key Social Studies topics, including concepts and objectives of Social Studies, family and marriage, culture, and socialization.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient determined the relationships between teaching competence variables (subject matter knowledge, methodology, classroom management, instructional material application, and evaluation strategies), teacher motivation, attitude, and students' performance. An independent t-test was conducted to compare the performance of students taught by trained vs. untrained social studies teachers. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (version 20), with the significance threshold set at $p < 0.05$.

Hypothesis 1: Relationship between Teachers' Competency and Students' Performance.

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Knowledge of the subject matter	90	44.00	92.00	67.5611	6.96737
Classroom management	90	46.00	90.00	66.5744	7.02860
Method of teaching	90	45.00	89.00	66.3744	6.86285
Application of instructional material	90	41.00	88.00	64.3033	7.25792
Evaluation strategies	90	43.00	88.00	68.7300	6.64480
Student academic achievement	90	40.00	92.00	67.6150	8.46628

Findings indicate that teachers' competency variables (subject knowledge, methodology, classroom management, instructional material usage, and evaluation strategies) were positively correlated with student performance. This supports previous research (Kosgei et al., 2013; Huang & Moon, 2009) that teacher competency accounts for 40-60% of student achievement.

Hypothesis 2: Relationship between Teachers' Motivation and Students' Academic Performance

Variables	N	df	r-cal	P-value	sig	Decision
Teachers' motivation and students' academic performance	90	88	0.217	0.04	0.05	H ₀ Rejected

The correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship ($r = 0.217$, $p = 0.04$) between teacher motivation and student achievement. Since $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that motivated teachers contribute to better student outcomes. This aligns with findings from Siddique (2010), emphasizing that teacher quality, motivation, and preparation significantly impact student learning.

Hypothesis 3: Relationship between Teachers’ Attitude and Students’ Performance

Variables	N	Df	r _{cal}	P-value	Sig.	Decision
Teachers attitudes and teachers’ response on students academic performance	90	88	.911	0.012	0.05	H ₀ Rejected

A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.911$, $p = 0.012$) was found between teachers' attitudes and student academic performance. This suggests that teachers' enthusiasm and engagement significantly enhance student learning, corroborating studies by Abioye & Sunday (2014) and Lydiah et al. (2014).

Hypothesis 4: Difference in Performance between Students Taught by Trained and Untrained Teachers

Group	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error
Students taught by professional teachers	254	73.55	4.54	0.28
Students taught by unprofessional teachers	46	55.61	10.32	1.52

T-Test Results

T-TEST RESULTS

Group	t-value	df	Sig. (p)	Mean Diff.	95% CI (lower-upper)
Students Taught by Trained Teachers	258.25	253	0.000	73.50	72.92-74.06
Students Taught by Untrained Teachers	36.52	45	0.000	55.56	52.49-58.62

The results showed a significant difference in performance between students taught by trained social studies teachers ($M = 73.55$) and those taught by untrained teachers ($M = 55.61$). The t-value ($t = 258.25$, $p < 0.000$) confirmed that trained teachers positively impact student performance, supporting findings from Darling-Hammond (2000) and Myrberg & Rosen (2001).

Discussion

The study confirmed that teacher competency, motivation, and attitude significantly influence students' academic performance in Social Studies.

1. Teachers' Competence and Student Performance

The findings corroborate Kosgei et al. (2013) and Huang & Moon (2009), indicating that teachers' mastery of subject matter, teaching methods, and classroom management enhances student learning outcomes.

A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.732$) was found between subject matter knowledge and student achievement, aligning with Abioye & Sunday (2014).

2. Teacher Motivation and Student Achievement

A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.217$) suggests that motivated teachers improve learning outcomes, supporting Siddique (2010) and Fakeye (2012).

3. Teachers' Attitude and Student Performance

A strong correlation ($r = 0.911$) emphasizes the importance of positive teacher attitudes, in line with studies by Lydiah et al. (2014) and Jadama (2014).

4. Influence of Trained vs. Untrained Social Studies Teachers on Students' Performance

A significant performance gap ($t = 258.25$, $p = 0.000$) between students taught by trained ($M = 73.55$) and untrained teachers ($M = 55.61$) validates findings by Darling-Hammond (2000) and Myrberg & Rosen (2001).

Classroom management, teaching methodology, and instructional materials directly influence student performance (Hanke et al., 2014; Adunola, 2011).

Conclusion

Based on the Findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. There is correlation between teachers' competence and students' performance in Junior Secondary School Social Studies in North-west Jigawa State.
2. The outcome of this research revealed the correlation between teachers' motivation and students' performance in Junior Secondary school Social Studies in North-west Jigawa State.
3. The result indicated how teachers' attitude correlates with students' performance in Junior Secondary School Social Studies in North-west Jigawa State.
4. It is also highlights differences in performance between set of students taught by qualified and those taught by unqualified Social Studies teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in North-west Jigawa State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. **Teacher Professional Development:** Continuous professional development programs, including seminars and workshops, should be organized to enhance teachers' competencies in instructional material utilization, classroom management, teaching methodologies, and evaluation strategies. Additionally, the government and relevant stakeholders should ensure the provision of adequate educational facilities.
2. **Improved Welfare for Teachers:** Teachers' salaries, promotions, and other benefits should be reviewed upward and paid promptly to enhance job satisfaction and commitment to effective teaching.
3. **Reorientation on Social Studies Education:** Teachers and students should be sensitized to the significance of Social Studies education in national development. This can be achieved through awareness campaigns and curriculum modifications that emphasize the subject's relevance.

4. Promotion of Gender Equity in Education: The government and other stakeholders should encourage free girl-child education and recruit more qualified female teachers to ensure gender equity and inclusivity in education.

5. Recruitment and Training of Qualified Social Studies Teachers: Teachers should be encouraged and sponsored to acquire relevant qualifications in Social Studies education, such as the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) and higher degrees. Only professionally trained and certified Social Studies teachers should be recruited to teach the subject.

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